

Title in FR and EN:

- Greening the Eurosystem: Analysing Euro central banks' debate on financial policies and their motivations against climate-related risks
- Un Eurosysteme écologisé : Analyser le débat et les motivations des Banques Centrales de l'Eurozone pour une politique financière verte

Abstract in French and English:

In this paper on Euro Central Banks and climate change, by analyzing the public discourse of Eurosystem central banks we seek to illustrate their behind closed doors debate on financial risks posed by the consequences of unmitigated climate change, along with the definition of their role and policies to adopt in dealing with them. To do so, we construct a database from available discourses pronounced by representatives of the French, German and Dutch national central banks, and the ECB, and classify them according to policy-type preference and motivation, revealing opposing interests and trends among Eurosystem banks' discourse on climate change.

Cet article sur les Banques Centrales Européennes et le changement climatique illustre, à travers des analyses de discours, le débat des banques centrales de l'Eurosysteme concernant les risques financiers que posent les conséquences du changement climatique, ainsi que leur rôle et politiques à adopter. Pour cela, l'on construit une base de données à partir des discours disponibles prononcés par des représentants de banques centrales française, allemande et hollandaise, ainsi que de la BCE, nous les classons par type de politiques et motivations de préférence, révélant des intérêts et tendances opposés

concernant le changement climatique entre membres de l'Eurosystème.

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1. Introduction:

The consequences of unmitigated climate change have been recognized by research as potentially ranging beyond physical and economic damages, into endangering the stability of the financial system as a whole. As several central bank mandates around the world include the responsibility of maintaining the stability of the financial system, their interest in researching the possible consequences of unmitigated climate change and ways to counter them has increased. (Campiglio et al., 2018, 466 ; Dikau and Volz, 2021, 19) In Europe one of the first instances of public discussion on the subject was the 2015 speech by the Governor of the Bank of England, Mark Carney, entitled “Tragedy over the horizon”, outlining the magnitude of environmental and social change and the shrinking window of action at our disposal. (Carney, 2015) Since, the debate in Europe has shifted from whether central banks should address the risks related to climate change, to how they should be addressed and what role should central banks play in the collective effort to counter them. With our ongoing research we seek to contribute to a better understanding of past negotiations among Eurosystem National Central Banks (NCBs) and the European Central Bank (ECB) that have shaped, and eventually led to, the current European stance on the role central banks should play in regards to climate change.

This paper stems from an academic exercise, carried out under a master’s degree to be further expanded upon in a potential future doctoral thesis. The continuation of research beyond our initial results here presented will establish a clearer timeline of events and dissemination of the potential factors at play, contributing to inform broader debates on the influence of domestic politics and circumstances in shaping the current ECB stance in regards to climate change, and it’s motives to differ from ones adopted in other regions of the world.

To carry out our research, we turn towards speeches by public figures of Eurosystem central banks, as a means to access their positioning and preferences around the debate on climate-related financial risks. We extract from the BIS (Bank of International Settlements) online database of central banker's speeches, along with the official websites of three NCBs (France, Germany and the Netherlands) and the ECB, selected as case studies, a total of 236 speeches mentioning climate related issues, pronounced between January 2015 and April 2022. We then proceed to their analysis, applying the taxonomy created by Baer et al. (2021) on central banks climate-related policies, for a classification of the motive and policy preferences of each central bank regarding the risks posed by climate change.

2. A European tragedy over the horizon: Climate risks, solutions, and Eurosystem dilemmas

2.1. Climate Related Financial Risks (CRFR) and the context of European central banking

The risks that climate change and its consequences pose to financial stability and economies at large has increasingly been debated among central banks in the last years. In western high-income countries this debate was first introduced among regulatory authorities by England's central bank governor, Mark Carney, who in a 2015 speech identified three types of risks relating to climate change: physical risks, resulting directly or indirectly from climate-prompted events and trends; liability risks, or losses sustained as a result of legal actions taken against companies and regulators' inaction against climate

change; and transition risks, financial risks caused by the shift towards a low-carbon economy. Since their introduction, these terms have been adopted, expanded, legitimized, and rebranded as Climate Related Financial Risks (CRFRs) by following research. (Carney, 2015 ; Chenet, Ryan-Collins and van Lerven, 2021 ; Dikau and Volz, 2021)

Initially, the debate focused on whether the risks associated with climate change should be taken into account by central banks with respect to their given mandates, centered on financial regulation and supervision. Once it was recognized among European central banks and academia that the accumulation of CRFRs could propagate through financial institutions, with the potential to become systemic if left unattended, the debate leaned towards how should central banks act in relation to climate change and its macroeconomic risk implications. (Batten, Sowerbutts and Tanaka, 2016 ; Bolton et al., 2020 ; Campiglio et al., 2018 ; Chenet, Ryan-Collins and van Lerven, 2021 ; Gros et al., 2016 ; NGFS, 2019 ; Semieniuk et al., 2021)

Theoretically, central banks hold a range of powerful tools that could be used in a more active role for promoting the greening of their economies. In their work Baer et al. (2021) compile into a taxonomy the potential climate-related financial policies that central banks could implement along three axis: policy instruments, policy motives, and implementing authority. Table 1 presents these different categories that we adopted for our analysis, while omitting the axis on implementing authority, as we focus solely on the potential actions taken by central banks as delegated authorities, and not political authorities.

[Table 1]

Informational instruments aim at providing financial market participants with larger amounts of improved information on climate-related risks (improving methodologies

assessing exposure to risk, homogenization of taxonomies, disclosure requirements, etc.). *Incentive-based instruments* seek to modify the incentives financial actors face in investment decision-making by rendering carbon-intensive assets riskier, while it is still possible to invest in them (for instance, targeting relative prices). *Quantity-based instruments* are a direct intervention from public institutions on the quantity of resources that can be allocated to specific productive activities through the imposition of direct quantitative controls on financial flows themselves, rather than indirectly by instead shaping the environment so as to protect free choice.

The second axis, policy motives, refers to the reasonings behind the implementation of the outlined policy types. *Prudential motives* applies to reasoning being the need to preserve overall financial stability in face of climate-related risks. *Promotional motives* instead seek to confront climate change and its consequences by directly influencing the allocation of capital through “market shaping” interventions. Promotional motives are therefore closely tied to quantity-based instruments.

Baer et al. (2021) find that the ECB’s institutional setting in the EU creates notable friction around the issue of which policy instruments should be adopted by central banks in reference to their current mandates, and which actions should be left to political authorities. The adoption of *Promotional motives* for a more active role from central banks against climate change, and their associated policies of direct intervention, away from current “free market” objectives, are particularly frowned upon due to potential redistributive consequences being unaccounted for under the current ECB mandate.

The combination of the ECB’s current narrow mandate centered on price stability and emphasis on avoiding “market distortions”, with its high degree of independence, makes coordination with its political authorities particularly challenging. A “double *impasse*” is

formed, where on one side the pursuit of green monetary policy without clear policy coordination with political authorities would mean overstepping the current understanding of its given mandate, while on the other, ignoring CRFRs and continuing to only pursue price stability without market distortions would make fulfilling said mandate progressively more difficult, as these risks materialize overtime. (Baer, Campiglio and Deyris, 2021 ; Dietsch et al., 2022)

As a consequence, when compared internationally, due to their self-imposed limitations, European central banks are found to over-emphasize *Prudential motives*, leading to what the authors of Baer et al. (2021) name a “promotional gap”. Especially relative to emerging economies, where promotional interventions are considered normal and socially useful to guide the allocation of resources and shape markets towards specific goals and developmental objectives. (Baer, Campiglio and Deyris, 2021) For instance, the People’s Bank of China promotes policy initiatives for green finance, stressing the need for central banks to provide policy incentives and contribute towards correct pricing of carbon emissions, so as to reduce them while bolstering green finance by financing “carbon emission reduction loans” at favorable interest rates. (Gang, 2021, 2023) The Reserve Bank of India, historically interventionist with credit allocation for priority sectors, is contributing to green finance development through its Priority Sector Lending, to which projects for renewable energy have been added, as well as issuing sovereign green bonds. (Rao, 2023) The Central Bank of Brazil, pioneering the implementation of green prudential and macroprudential policy, has been a first in mainstreaming environmental and social risk¹ management with binding regulation requiring banks to self-asses their exposure to climate risks. (Ryan-Collins and Dikau, 2017)

¹ Environmental and social risks (E&S risk) refer to potential negative repercussions for businesses, consequence of the impact their actions have on nature’s environment (water resources, air, soil, etc.) and communities of people. They are conceived in relation to “traditional risks”, which E&S risks can drive up through different “transmission channels”. (European Banking Authority, 2023, 24-27)

2.2. Policy discrepancies behind the Eurosystem veil:

With all of the aforementioned, we find it fair to state that climate change represents a major dilemma for both the ECB and NCBs forming the Eurosystem, holding implications beyond purely economics, and questioning the overall role and place of central banks. On account of these overarching implications, this becomes a political question for the Eurosystem central banks, comparable to the identity-changing moments endured during the debt crisis, for which an easily reached consensus is hard to imagine. We therefore build our argument from the assumption that an internal debate has been taking place among Eurosystem members on CRFRs. This cannot be observed directly as the Governing Council of the Eurosystem², its main decision-making body, does not disclose individual voting records from the participating governors, and debates take place behind closed doors, seeking to portray consensus among the Eurozone decisions, driven by “technical” economic factors rather than political ones.

However, findings by Moschella and Diodati (2020) demonstrate the existence of internal disagreement among NCBs of the Eurosystem and the ECB, and the influence of political factors on their outcomes. Their findings also show that despite moderating themselves in favor of an image of cohesion and consensus during formal deliberations, back home NCBs use public discourse to influence future decisions. Therefore contributing to the ever-growing body of research recognizing central bank’s public speech as a relevant method for their analysis, with communication being adopted by central banks as a way of posturing in relation to markets (Guthrie and Wright, 2000 ; Hubert and Labondance, 2021 ; Moschella and Diodati, 2020 ; Schmeling and Wagner, 2015). This is also supported by

² The Governing Council of the Eurosystem is formed by the six members of the ECB’s Executive Board, and the Governor of each NCB of the Euroarea, for a total of 26 members as of 2023.

the findings of Deyris (2022) who, using public speech analysis and interviews with insiders, illustrates the evolution of the ECB's Governing Council internal debate for the integration of climate change onto the ECB policies.

Consequently, we envision the possibility of studying internal disagreements among Eurosystem members through public speech on the subject of how central banks should deal with CRFRs, and which are the dominant motives behind it. Taking into account previous academic findings and the aforementioned context, we formulate the following hypotheses:

- Following the conclusions by Baer et al. (2022) pointing to the existence of a “promotional gap” in European central banking actions regarding CRFRs, we expect to see this reflected in our analysis with a general majority and consensus towards favoring informational policies and prudential motives.

H1: Informational policies with prudential motives represent the position most frequently expressed by the Eurozone against CRFRs.

- Based on the findings by Moschella and Diodati (2022), and Deyris (2022), we expect to observe divergences between NCBs and the ECB on policy preferences regarding CRFRs.

H2: NCBs show divergent policy preferences with respect to the ones proposed by the ECB on how to deal with climate related risks.

3. Building and framing a database on climate-related speeches:

To conduct our research we analyze the discourse of the ECB and NCBs of the Eurosystem on the issue of climate change, focusing on stated opinions on the role that central banks should play as delegated authorities. To do so, we construct our corpus of research from available online speeches on both official websites of the central banks selected as case studies, and on the BIS when not available on the corresponding official

websites. We limit our timeframe between the year 2015 and the 15th of June 2022. In 2015, then-Governor of the Bank of England, Mark Carney, delivered the speech “Breaking the Tragedy of the Horizon”, which we identify as the starting point of the debate among European central banks regarding CRFRs and how to address them. (Carney, 2015)

We initially conduct a preliminary sweep around the available online speeches of the ECB and all other NCBs of the Eurosystem on the subject matter by searching their official websites for a substantial numbers of speeches containing the words “green” or “climate” on their title or description. We only consider speeches that have been pronounced in English, or those which had available English translations online, as we conceptualize speeches with a provided English translation as having a more direct connection to an international audience and debates, therefore closer to European discussions on climate change³. Reading only those pronounced by Governors of the institutions as a starting point, we select the French central bank Banque de France, the German central bank Deutsche Bundesbank, and the Dutch central bank De Nederlandsche Bank, due to them presenting similar levels of available speeches on the matter in English.

All French, German, and Dutch NCBs are substantial players in the Eurosystem monetary landscape, their economies ranking in weight among the top five in the Eurozone⁴, but also politically with their countries being founding members of the European Union. Beyond this, France and Germany, along with their preferences on economic understandings, played a key role in shaping the creation of the European Monetary Union (EMU) as well

³ Out of the three NCBs selected for our analysis (France, Germany, Netherlands) only the German NCB presents speeches without an available English translation. These are small in numbers (17 speeches without translation) against the total number of speeches available online, and only one of them would be eligible under our criteria presented further ahead (p. 13).

⁴ Ranked by Gross Domestic Product at market prices as of 2022 (Eurostat, 2023)

as in managing it during times of crisis. During the years of the sovereign debt crisis they assumed a shared role of leadership with significant influence on the resulting outcomes and changes to the EMU. (Feld, Köhler and Nientiedt, 2015 ; Lovering, 2023 ; Schmidt, 2016) Since 2019 Christine Lagarde, former French minister of finance, leads the ECB as its President. Isabel Schnabel, former member of the German Council of Economic Experts, is also a member of the ECB Executive Board since 2020⁵. Finally, the Dutch NCB, despite its smaller economic weight in the Euro-zone, is consistently a loud voice in European debates on economic issues, and its NCB has lead research on climate change. (Siderius, 2023) Frank Elderson, who during the years prior to joining the ECB led the Dutch NCB efforts on sustainable finance, is a member of the ECB executive board since 2020.

We wish we could have also taken into account more data from what Deyris (2022) identifies as “[...] central bankers in “frugal” countries such as Belgium, Austria, and Germany.” (Deyris, 2022, 21), in regards to questions on the potential of the second mandate of the ECB to provide a sufficient basis for further climate action, but unfortunately the number of publicly available online speeches from both Austria and Belgium were very limited. NCBs from other regions of the Eurozone were also taken into account as potential case studies for a more complete picture. Spain and Italy both also have economies that rank in the top 5 by weight in the Eurozone and have nationals currently sitting as members of the ECB Executive Board as of 2023, but while substantial numbers of available online speeches are available, few of them dealt with the subject of climate change and risks in comparison to the selected case studies. NCBs from Central and Eastern European countries of the Euro Zone displayed a reduced number of online available speeches, with few, if any, dealing with climate change and risks.

⁵ The monetary policy of the Euro Area is set by the Governing Council, composed by the governors of the NCBs in the Eurosystem and the six members (including the ECB’s President) sitting on the Executive Council of the ECB, responsible for implementing its monetary policy.

Table 2 summarizes our corpus of research obtained from the selected case studies, displaying for each case and year the total number of speeches found, the number of which contained valid units of analysis, and how many units were identified for their analysis.

[Table 2]

To compile our corpus we first manually scrape their websites and the ECBs, complemented by the BIS central bank speeches database, through which we cross-reference every speech found, in case any would be available on the BIS database but not on the ECB/NCBs website. Therefore every speech is downloaded, and the words “climate” and/or “green” are searched using a word browsing tool, to be found at least once in order to count as a speech selected for analysis. A total of $n=234$ speeches were selected under this criteria, containing at least one mention of climate change. Each of the 234 speeches was read in its entirety with two objectives: identify and remove “false positives” derived from our initial selection (e.g. “business climate”, “political climate”), and identify paragraphs in which the central banks state policy preferences on how they should act in reference to climate change (sometimes a paragraph does address climate change but does not express opinions on how central banks should act in regards to it). Having fulfilled this task the number of speeches fit for our analysis is reduced to a new total of 126. Each paragraph found to contain information regarding the policy preferences and motivations of the central bank is counted as a single unit of analysis, resulting in a total of 401 units of analysis among the four selected case studies. Some flexibility was occasionally required when determining what constitutes a unit of analysis, as the speech transcripts sometimes cut into two paragraphs mid-sentence, or a large paragraph is followed by a second, much shorter one, that is in clear direct connection with the first. In these cases these were counted as a single unit of analysis, as counting them separately

would wrongly reflect a repetition that is not representative of the speaker's intention. For instance, the following two paragraphs were considered as a single unit of analysis:

“For our part, the ECB is carefully studying the potential impact of climate-related risks for the euro area financial system.

We are currently developing an analytical framework for carrying out a climate risk stress test analysis for the euro area banking sector. The pilot test framework will be macroprudential in nature, and allow us to analyse the system-wide materiality of transition risks for banks' solvency, along with their lending capacity and the implications for the overall economy. The eventual aim is to incorporate both physical and transitional risks, and investigate how these two types of risks interact with each other.” (de Guindos, 2019)

The text contained in each unit is then extracted into a table where they are compiled and individually analyzed for their classification, according to the taxonomy introduced by Baer et al. (2021) as previously presented in Table 1.

Beyond counting the number of mentions each actor makes for each category, we also consider whether it is mentioned in a positive or negative way, as in being in favor or against it. Therefore number 1 is assigned to positive mentions; -1 to negative mentions; and 0 when the policy or motivation at hand is not mentioned in the analyzed unit (to be counted as a unit it has to at least present one positive or negative mention).

For instance:

“There is a strong case for mandatory climate-related disclosures. More and better information will help companies and financial institutions to improve their risk management and their decision-making more generally.” (Weidmann, 2021, 3)

This quote from a speech by then-Governor of the Deutsche Bundesbank, Jens Weidmann, is read as being in favor of informational policies with a prudential motive behind them. Promoting higher quantities and quality of climate-related information is emphasized, going as far as to suggest making them mandatory, as improved information on climate is expected to help market actors better manage risk (prudential motive).

On the other hand, the following quote, also by Jens Weidmann as Governor of the Deutsche Bundesbank, showcases an example of negative mentions:

"Second, it is not the task of the Eurosystem to penalise or subsidise certain industries. Correcting market distortions often has intricate distributional implications. Such decisions need strong democratic legitimacy and are a matter for governments and parliaments. They have the right tools at their disposal and, as elected representatives, they also have the democratic authority to use those tools. At the same time, they have to weigh the fight against climate change against other policy goals." (Weidmann, 2020, 5)

The introduction of incentive-based policies for market corrections induced by climate issues is presented as beyond the realm of the Eurosystem, stating redistribution consequences and a lack of democratic legitimacy from central banks to justify them compared to governments. Further, the role of elected representatives as main actors against climate change is underlined, which we interpret as against central banks adopting promotional motives, instead reserved for government and parliament. Therefore this unit is classed as stating to be against incentive-based policies and promotional motives.

Once all the paragraphs have been identified as units, analyzed, and classified according to the Baer et al. (2021) taxonomy, the results are added up and the final values are presented for their subsequent analysis and interpretation, as shown in Table 3.

Ideally, in order to avoid over-subjective interpretations, this classification would be carried out by multiple investigators independently and then compared to reduce subjectivity. In this case the limitations of this academic exercise made this impossible. Other works such as the one published by Deyris (2022), also touch on the subject of consensus formation on climate change among the ECB Governing Council, expanding beyond the constraints of our analysis. In this case mixed methods are employed for a more holistic representation of the debate that took place behind doors, combining the examination of speeches and communications with exchanges between Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) and the ECB, a systematic review of regulation and policy documents of the ECB on climate, and eleven semi-structured interviews with central bankers from the ECB and different NCBs, as well as with MEPs on the ECON committee⁶. This more thorough approach allows for greater informed findings with improved contextualization, which we will later reference in relation to ours. (Deyris, 2022) More complex forms of discourse analysis employ computer processing techniques under a statistical approach, revealing tendencies in wording and tone. For instance, Massart (2022) employs lexicometry techniques to analyze differences in the discourse employed by the EU with different Member States regarding the European Semester, allowing for a description and characterization of a large corpus of discourses. (Massart, 2022) The possible utilization of such statistical and computer processing techniques for our work was considered and consulted with academic scholars experienced in their use, who advised against it as unnecessary in reference to the size of our corpus, complexity of our intended analysis, and limits in time and resources.

⁶ The Committee on Economic and Monetary Affairs (known as ECON) is a permanent committee of the European Parliament. MEPs who participate in it follow the economic and monetary affairs of the EU, notably the actions undertaken by the ECB.

4. Obtained results and future hypothesis:

Looking at our initial results, prior to 2018 the ECB shows no speeches and therefore no mentions of what policies should be adopted, corroborating the findings by Deyris (2022). In comparison, the NCBs show mentions in their speeches on how to address climate change prior to the ECB's first mention in 2018. The Dutch NCB in particular shows an early interest, along with the French NCB.

This delay in the ECB publicly expressing its position could be connected to the resolution in 2020 of internal tension around the issue of climate change in the ECB executive board, as pointed out by Deyris (2022), and subsequent heavy featuring of climate change in the 2021 strategy review of the ECB. (Deyris, 2022, 13)

[Table 3]

Table 3 introduces the percentage of overall mentions of climate-related policies, distinguishing between positive and negative assessments of different motives and policies. We identify as general trends that both ECB and the NCBs align overwhelmingly around expressing a positive opinion of prudential motives and informational policies. This aligns as expected in regards to Baer et al. (2021), and therefore confirms our hypothesis n°1. On the opposite end, also as anticipated, overall promotional motives and quantity-based policies receive the least positive mentions. Performing this in a democratically legitimate way would have to reflect a response to an explicit re-organization of their mandate and mission by political authorities. Nor does it indicate that the central banks' "loneliness" is pushing them to go promotional without a mandate.

(Baer, Campiglio and Deyris, 2021, 7)

The main difference from the lowest common denominator of informational policies and prudential motives (Baer, Campiglio and Deyris, 2021) is the significant positive featuring of incentive-based policies, representing a deviation from the strict understanding of European central bank's mandates, due to the questioning of their central element of market neutrality. More interestingly, we notice a significant alignment between the ECB and the French NCB around a favorable view of incentive-based policies once the European authority starts expressing its view on the matter. This sharing of policy preferences leads us to theorize on successful efforts by the French NCB in promoting their views during the debate at European level. Conversely, the German NCB shows the highest percentage of overall negative mentions, always in regards to incentive-based policies and prudential motives, suggesting Germany as the main opposition to deviating away from the status quo role. Prior findings support this notion by identifying Germany as one of the "frugal" countries during the ECB's internal debate on potentially addressing climate issues through its second mandate, in opposition to the idea of moving away from the current narrow mandate of financial stability. (Deyris, 2022, 21) Finally, the Dutch NCB would seem to be in support of the French NCB's enthusiasm for incentive-based policies, although at a slightly lower rate of 16% on its overall mentions on climate related policies, leading us to hypothesize the possibility of a coalition of sorts with the French NCB, as the Dutch NCB has been pointed out as an unexpected early proponent of further action on climate. (Siderius, 2023)

[Figure 1]

For a better understanding of the apparent dilemma around incentive-based policies identified in Table 3 we turn to Figure 1, displaying by year the number of positive

mentions for incentive-based policies by the French and Dutch NCBs; and of negative mentions for incentive-based policies and promotional motives by the German central bank, allowing us to compare these evolutions to the ECB's known outcome in favor of incentive-based policies.

We identify 2019 as the year of highest tension with the highest levels of both positive and negative mentions from all NCBs, marking the moment prior to the resolution of tensions in 2020 and swaying the ECB. This all fits in the window of time described by (Deyris, 2022, 11) of internal discussion in the ECB on climate issue in regards to their mandate and policies between 2018 and 2020. 2020 represents a drop from all opinions in numbers, while 2021 suggests revealing the "winners" of the NCBs struggle for influencing the ECB's official position, with a sudden rise of positive mentions for incentive-based policies from the ECB only matched from the French NCB, followed by the Dutch. This further reinforces our conception of French success in influencing the debate, along with encountering multiple mentions of praise towards Christine Lagarde (President of the ECB since 2019), and her politics on climate change, something that is never replicated by the two other NCBs, leading us to a hypothetical relation between the naming of Lagarde as President of the ECB during its internal debate, and the prevalence of the French NCB policy preferences over climate issues to be explored in further research on the subject. This is reinforced by previous findings on the replacement of the ECB Executive Board as the main reason for the central bank's shift towards integrating climate change (Deyris, 2022), and on national influences and weight of domestic political considerations over the ECB (Moschella and Diodati, 2020).

On the other hand, we see a clear potential explanation for the evolution of the Dutch NCB. Showing a significant drop after 2019 on positive mentions of incentive-based policies and never recovering, the departure of Frank Elderson from the Dutch NCB, him

being the maximum proponent in favor of incentive-based policies with overall 9 positive mentions, to the Executive Board of the ECB in 2020 could be a potential hypothesis to be explored.

We also observe in our initial findings that the drop in German negative mentions of incentive-based policies from 2019 is accompanied by a further rise of unfavorable mentions on promotional motives in 2021. Relating this observation to the statement by Deyris (2022) on how in order for the climate issue to be mainstreamed into ECB policies a compromise had to be reached, in which promotional motives would be abandoned and the ECB secondary mandate would not be invoked to guide climate related policies (Deyris, 2022, 21-22), we therefore interpret that Germany lost its push against incentive-based policies but won its bid against promotional motives.

By 2021 the ECB's stance on climate-related policies is set on positively viewing incentive-based ones but is restricted to prudential motives, the French NCB can overtly support incentive-based policies along with the Dutch, while Germany increases its discourse against promotional motives, with all parties involved falling back into upholding an image of unity behind the ECB's voice and among Eurosystem members, as a compromise had been reached. In any case, further research with further resources, including all of the NCBs, should be conducted and able to represent a clearer and more complete picture of the situation, capable of illustrating behind-the-scenes preferences and potentially their relation with domestic political contexts.

Finally, regarding our hypothesis n°2, rather than the NCBs expressing disparity in their policy preferences in relation to the ECB, early results show disparity among themselves on the issue on how central banks should deal with climate change. This divergence may

sway the ECB's perspective to one of the ends.

In conclusion, through our initial findings we understand that the debate on climate change among European central banks was initially led by the NCBs who, at different levels and timings, first integrated the subject into their public speeches. This leads us to conceive the ECB not as an early public participant in this debate, pushing the subject of climate and its own preferences, but rather as a central actor in a passive role, to be influenced by NCB preferences struggling among each other to make their inclinations become the ECB's. Ultimately, the debate's outcome did not fundamentally challenge the status quo positioning of prudential motives in relation to CRFRs, and a preference for informational policies. Still, incentive-based policies were addressed in a positive note by the ECB in their speeches, challenging to some extent market-neutrality dogmas of European central banking, despite retaining prudential motives as rationale. This slight deviation in praise of incentive-based policies by the ECB seems to align with French preferences, as shown by our initial results. In addition, the fact that promotional motives are never addressed by the ECB and only opposed by the German NCB, identified as one of the "frugal" countries (Deyris, 2022, 21), compliments suggestions made by other authors on the ECB's public stance being the result of a compromise between NCBs' opposing preferences. (Deyris, 2022)

Further research on the subject should seek to include all other NCBs from the Eurozone, and expand the research methodology beyond our analysis of public speeches, potentially identifying factions between European central banks, and if their positioning on climate deviates from their usual approach, such as in the Dutch case (Siderius, 2023). Likewise, future efforts should look into the potential link between NCB's positioning on climate and their domestic political factors, such as the level of consensus around climate issues, as it

has been suggested (Deyris, 2023, 215). Lastly, France's apparent successful influence on the ECB and Lagarde's nomination are worth being examined more closely in regards to recent theorizations of a growing French influence among EU politics (Bora and Schramm, 2023).

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Tables and figures:

Policy instruments	
Informational	Improving the quality and abundance of climate-related information for market participants (improved methodologies, taxonomies, disclosure requirements, etc.)
Incentive-based	Modifying the incentives financial actors face during investment decision-making by rendering carbon-intensive assets riskier (monetary incentives for targeting relative prices, for example)
Quantity-based	Direct intervention by public authorities for the imposition of quantitative controls on financial flows
Policy motives	
Prudential	Ensuring overall financial stability in relation to climate-related risks
Promotional	Challenge climate change and its consequences by steering credit towards low-carbon activities

Table 1. Taxonomy of Climate-related financial policies (Baer et al., 2021, 3)

		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total
EU	Total found speeches	0	0	0	2	1	3	17	5	28
	With valid units of analysis	0	0	0	2	1	3	13	5	24
	Nº of units of analysis	0	0	0	6	5	9	45	18	83
FR	Total found speeches	1	2	6	8	17	10	16	9	69
	With valid units of analysis	1	0	0	4	9	5	10	7	36
	Nº of units of analysis	6	0	0	13	19	9	35	13	95
DE	Total found speeches	4	1	6	9	21	22	27	16	106
	With valid units of analysis	0	0	2	0	9	10	16	4	41
	Nº of units of analysis	0	0	4	0	40	35	41	8	128
NL	Total found speeches	1	0	4	4	8	4	3	7	31
	With valid units of analysis	1	0	4	4	6	2	2	6	25
	Nº of units of analysis	2	0	10	16	25	5	10	27	95

Table 2. Collected data between 2015 and 2022 by case and year for the number of found speeches, speeches which have valid units of analysis, and nº of units of analysis (combined data from the central banks and BIS websites)

% of positive mentions	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based
EU	83%	1%	74%	23%	0%
FR	74%	1%	77%	28%	0%
DE	82%	0%	74%	4%	0%
NL	77%	0%	81%	16%	0%
% of negative mentions	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based
EU	0%	0%	0%	5%	2%
FR	0%	2%	0%	2%	4%
DE	0%	13%	0%	9%	0%
NL	0%	1%	0%	1%	0%

Table 3. Overall percentage of positive and negative mentions of motives and policies by each central bank, in relation to

its total number of identified units of analysis between 2015 and 2022. (Combined data from the central banks and BIS websites)

Annex:

Annex 1: Overall positive and negative mentions in percentage and absolute numbers per case

POSITIVE						
Units of positive mentioning	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based	Total of units of analysis
EU	71	1	63	20	0	87
FR	70	1	73	27	0	95
DE	112	0	101	6	0	137
NL	74	0	78	14	0	95
Positive mentioning percentage	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based	
EU	83%	1%	74%	23%	0%	
FR	74%	1%	77%	28%	0%	
DE	82%	0%	74%	4%	0%	
NL	77%	0%	81%	16%	0%	
NEGATIVE						
Units of negative mentioning	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based	Total units of analysis
EU	0	0	0	4	2	87
FR	0	2	0	2	4	95
DE	0	18	0	12	0	137
NL	0	1	0	1	0	96
Negative mentioning percentage	Prudential	Promotional	Informational	Incentive-based	Quantity-based	
EU	0%	0%	0%	5%	2%	
FR	0%	2%	0%	2%	4%	
DE	0%	13%	0%	9%	0%	
NL	0%	1%	0%	1%	0%	

